

Studies in Light Absorption and Refractive Index of Chromium Tellurate Sol

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Chromium tellurate sol has been prepared and its extinction and refractive index have been studied. The extinction decreases due to removal of coloured chromium ions and increases on account of the colloidal particles. When a definite network of colloidal particle shape has been formed, the magnitude of increase in extinction with the growth in particle size just compensates the decrease due to Cr^{3+} ions. Similar is the case with refractive index.

In the study of colloids, spectrophotometric and photometric methods were used for the first time by Mukherjee and Papaconstantinou¹. Since then several workers have employed different optical methods with various purposes in the study of colloids. Thus La Mer and co-workers² studied the phenomenon of light scattering by sulphur sols and prepared monodispersed sols with particle size lying between 0.20μ and 0.65μ . The particle-size determination was carried out with spectrophotometric transmission method by Weneck and Eshler³. Troelstra and Kruyt⁴ studied the coagulation of silver iodide and ferric hydroxide sols by light-extinction measurements. From the study of extinction-concentration curves at coagulation time, they concluded that the particles formed by univalent ions were more compact than those by multivalent ions. Chatterji and Tawari⁵ studied the effect of non-electrolytes on the kinetics of coagulation of As_2S_3 and $Fe(OH)_3$ sols and found that whereas some non-electrolytes caused coagulation, others led to the stabilisation of sols. Nakagaki⁶ gave a theoretical treatment for extinction, scattering, and transmission of light by coloured colloidal systems of small spherical particles. The values of extinction coefficient obtained from his approximate equation are in fair agreement with those obtained from Mie's theory.

From what has been said above, it is clear that studies in absorption of light and refractive index can provide useful information about colloids. Hence the authors have carried out experiments in extinction and refractive index of chromium tellurate sol at various stages of dialysis.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chromium tellurate sol was prepared by mixing 0.5% potassium tellurate solution with 13.0929% of chromium chloride solution in the ratio of 11:1 by volume and kept for dialysis. Water was changed every 24 hours. The sol set to a gel in 30 days.

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 1563.
2. La Mer and Barnes, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1946, 1, 7, 71; Johnson and La Mer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 1184; Zaiser and La Mer, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1949, 3, 571; Drozin and La Mer, *ibid.*, 1959, 14, 74.
3. *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1959, 14, 308.
4. *Kolloid-Beihfte*, 1943, 54, 225.
5. *This Journal*, 1954, 31, 881.
6. *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1958, 31, 980.

The extinction measurements were carried out with photoelectric colorimeter (Lichtelektrisches Kolorimeter Model IV). Blue filter was chosen as it allowed the maximum extinction for chromium tellurate sol; 10-ml cuvettes were used. Refractive index was determined by Abbe's refractometer.

Standard methods were used for the determination of the composition of the sol at various stages of dialysis. Tellurate was estimated by reduction to tellurium with hydrazine hydrochloride and saturated sulphur dioxide solution⁸. Chromium was determined volumetrically by oxidation with sodium peroxide and titration with standardised ferrous sulphate solution, using diphenylamine as an indicator. Chloride estimation was carried out by Volhard's method.

TABLE I

Stage of dialysis.	No. of days.	Ref. index.	Extinction.	Cr ³⁺ .	TeO ₄ ²⁻ .	Cl ⁻ .
I	0	1.3340	0.390	0.21280	0.2432	0.4415
II	3	1.3335	0.340	0.15890	0.1486	0.2281
III	6	1.3328	0.320	0.13120	0.1051	0.1546
IV	9	1.3322	0.312	0.09390	0.0907	0.0844
V	12	1.3320	0.310	0.07290	0.0751	0.0402
VI	15	1.3320	0.310	0.05540	0.0693	0.0234
VII	17	1.3320	0.310	0.05230	0.0676	0.0184
VIII	19	1.3320	0.310	0.04760	0.0669	0.0161
IX	21	1.3320	0.310	0.04450	0.0626	0.0122
X	23	1.3320	0.310	0.04410	0.0613	0.0097
XI	28	1.3320	0.310	0.03955	0.0592	0.0034
Water	..	1.3300	0.0			

DISCUSSION

It will be observed from curve A in Fig. 1 that at the initial stages (I & II; Table I, column 4) there is a rapid and almost linear decrease in extinction, followed by an exponential decrease (III to V) and from the fifth stage onwards there is no change in extinction.

So far as refractive index is concerned, there is a linear decrease almost to the fourth stage (Curve B in Fig. 1), then an exponential decrease, and from the fifth stage onwards it becomes constant as in the case of light extinction.

For extinction by chromium tellurate sol, the contribution to absorption of light will be by coloured chromium ions and the colloidal particles of chromium tellurate. A rapid decrease in the initial stage can easily be attributed to the fast removal of chromium ions in the early stages of dialysis, though the changes in the particles of disperse phase may also make some contribution to it. Due to removal of chromium ions, the light absorption will decrease continuously, first rapidly and then slowly (vide Table I, column 5) with the progress of dialysis till almost the last stages. Actually, the absorption is constant from the fifth stage onwards.

This can only be explained by assuming that as the colloidal particles increase in size with the removal of other ions, absorption also increases but slowly and the magnitude

FIG. 1 Variation in extinction and ref. index of Cr-tellurate sol with progress of dialysis.

of increase is small. In the early stages, the increase in absorption is more than compensated by the decrease due to chromium ions. When the fifth stage is reached, as the rate of removal of chromium ions is less, the increase in absorption due to colloidal particles is just compensated for the decrease owing to removal of chromium ions or the difference is too small to be detected. Further, in the growth of colloidal particles, which are non-spherical in shape, by the time the fifth stage is reached, the nucleus of the network for the shape of the colloidal particles is complete and though the growth continues, the overall shape of the particles remains the same till they finally set to a jelly.

These views are supported by the study of refractive index. The decrease in refractive index is more uniform because besides Cr^{3+} ions, other ions (viz., K^+ , Cl^- , and TeO_4^{4-}) also make their contribution to it. The contribution of the sol particles is one of slow and small increase in refractive index with the particle size. When the fifth stage is reached and definite shape of network of colloidal particles is formed, any slight increase in the density of aggregates is partly neutralised by decrease in Brownian movement, thus slowing down the decrease in refractive index contribution of the sol particles.

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